

ISic3701

I.Sicily inscription 3701

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

found in the foundations of S. Catharinae Senensis coenobii, 1702

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140867

1. ἔζησεν Μαρτ[ύ]ριος ἔτη εἴκοσι δύο.
2. εἰρήνη σοι. \square c ²⁶Χρ(ιστός)²⁶.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 140867

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.*. Berlin.

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Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus
Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 4.9486

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edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4389001>